

ENHANCING LANGUAGE TEACHING THROUGH THE IMPLEMENTATION OF DYNAMIC ASSESSMENT

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For some years traditional forms of assessment were dominant in the field of language testing. According to Garb (2008, cited in Xiaoxiao & Yan, 2010) traditional summative assessment attempts to summarize learners' learning at some point in time, say the end of a course, but cannot provide the immediate, contextualized feedback useful for helping teacher and learners during the learning process. He describes DA as a way of assessing the true potential of children that extends the interactive nature of leaning to the process of assessment. The teacher and the learners come into a dialogue to find out the learners' current level of performance on any task and share with each other the possible ways in which that performance might be improved on a subsequent occasion. This deliberate and planned meditational teaching and the assessment becomes an integral and continuous process. In DA the teacher acts as an improvement promoter and provides immediate and situated feedback during the whole procedure; moreover, the focus of DA is learners' future development, not the outcome of the past development (Garb, 2008, cited in Xiaoxiao & Yan, 2010).

Moreover, as Lidz (1987) states DA challenges conventional views on teaching and assessment by arguing that these should not be seen as separate activities but should instead be fully integrated. This integration occurs as intervention is embedded within the assessment procedure in order to interpret individuals' abilities and lead them to higher levels of functioning. The unification of assessment and instruction is grounded in Vygotsky's understanding of development.

According to Haywood and Lidz (2007, p. 1) the dynamic assessment website defines DA as "an interactive approach to conducting assessment within the domains of psychology, speech/language, or education that focuses on the ability of the learner to respond to intervention." They maintain that what is the major component of definitions provided so far for DA is "active intervention by examiners and assessment of examinee's response to intervention." (p. 1)

Haywood and Tzuriel (2002, cited in Haywood & Lidz, 2007, p. 2) define dynamic assessment as "a subset of interactive assessment that includes deliberate and planned meditational teaching and the assessment of the effects of that teaching on subsequent performance."

The advent of DA is relatively new in the field of educational assessment in general and in the field of second language assessment in particular (Ableeva, 2009). Tzuriel and Shamir (2007) states that there has recently been a proliferation of interest in DA due to the current dissatisfaction with static standardized testing procedures. In their definition of DA, Lantolf and Poehner (2004) state that “in essence, DA is a procedure for simultaneously assessing and promoting development that takes account of the individual’s (or group’s) zone of proximal development” (p. 50). In other words, Lantolf and Poehner define DA in terms of one’s zone of proximal development, a major concept in Vygotsky’s Socio-Cultural Theory (SCT). This definition also reveals that DA aims at promoting examinees’ development rather than measuring their performance at a specific point of time. Lidz (1987), on the other hand, defines DA as “an interaction between an examiner-as-intervener and a learner-as-active participant, which seeks to estimate the degree of modifiability of the learner and the means by which positive changes in cognitive functioning can be induced and maintained” (p. 4).

Both of the aforementioned two definitions of DA emphasize that this assessment procedure seeks to assess learners’ potential development rather than assessing their current abilities or performances which is a main feature distinguishing DA from traditional Non-Dynamic Assessment (NDA) procedures.

It is worth noting that whereas Lidz’s (1987) definition seems to emphasize that the goal of DA is mainly to achieve cognitive modifiability, more recent definitions of DA (e.g., Ableeva, 2009; Anton, 2009; Poehner, 2005) stress the social rather than cognitive aspect of this assessment procedure. In fact, recent research on DA (e.g., Haywood & Tzuriel, 1992) refers to this assessment procedure as *interactive assessment* which emphasizes the social and interactive nature of DA. The social aspect of DA is manifested in the nature of the mediator-learner interactions in which the mediator is seen as an intervener aiming at developing the learner’s potential ability and the examinee is seen as an involved active participant. This difference between earlier and more recent definitions of DA can be attributed to the nature of the learner population assessed using this assessment method. That is, earlier work on DA examined the effect of this procedure on children with learning disabilities, so the focus was on modifying their cognitive abilities; on the other hand, more recent work on DA is interested in promoting the learning potential of second language learner populations. Thus, due to the interactive nature of DA, it could be said that another characteristic defining DA and distinguishing it from static NDA is its focus on the importance of examiner-examinee interactions which aim at promoting learner development.

Another distinction between DA and NDA is that whereas a major goal of the former is to bridge the gap between assessment and instruction, the latter does not seem to be interested in the impact of tests on instruction. Lantolf and Poehner (2004) contend that “dynamic assessment integrates assessment and instruction into a seamless, unified activity aimed at promoting learner development through appropriate forms of mediation that are sensitive to the individual’s (or in some cases a group’s) current abilities” (p. 50). Hence, as Poehner (2008) rightly asserts, the concept of DA can help “reconceptualize classroom interactions by arguing that teaching and assessment should not be distinct undertakings but must be integrated as a single activity that seeks to understand learners abilities by actively supporting their ongoing development”(p. 203).

To sum up, DA seems to differ from NDA in a number of ways including: (1) its focus on learners’ potential abilities provided that they are assisted with appropriate mediation, and (2) its emphasis on the importance of uniting assessment and instruction so that assessment is considered a means by which instructional decisions can be made rather than an end in itself.

Brown’s Graduated Prompt Approach.

Brown and her colleagues have devised a series of DA procedures for specific content domains, focusing especially on reading and math with normal and special children (see Brown and Ferrera, 1985; Brown et al., 1984). Like other interventionist approaches to DA, the Graduated Prompt approach relies on a fixed menu of standardized hints and leading questions that are used during the administration of the test after each item or problem. This mediation is arranged from most implicit to most explicit and culminates with the correct answer. The unique contribution of the Graduated Prompt approach, and what makes it especially important from a Vygotskian perspective, is its inclusion of *transfer tasks*.

In their procedures, examinees are first presented with questions or tasks and, when they experience difficulties, the examiner offers mediation intended to help them discover and applied principles necessary for solving the problems. Once these are mastered so that the examinees can solve the problems independently, the researchers then attempt to discover how far the individuals can transfer their new ability to novel problems. Thus, these Brown offers a dimension to the emerging picture of development that was absent from the other DA approaches we have considered. Guthke, basing his argument on the ZPD, suggested that perfect performance on the posttest is not the sole indication that development has occurred; it may be the case that learners have developed and now require fewer and less explicit prompts. Brown and her colleagues, also drawing on Vygotsky, claim that an

additional and crucial feature of development is that an individual's performance change not only on a repetition of the original test (or a parallel test) but on different kinds of tasks.

After examinees are able to independently solve “novel exemplars” of the original problem types, they are given a set of “near transfer” problems which integrate the same principles as the original task but in new combinations (Campione et al., 1984, p. 81). Then the examinees are presented with a set of “far transfer” problems requiring “the use of a new but related rule or principle in addition to the familiar ones”. Finally, the examinees are asked to respond to a set of “very far transfer” problems that are even more complex. Based on the examinees' performance throughout the procedure, the researchers generate learner profiles comprising two axes – one measuring how quickly they are able to learn the new patterns and the other measuring how far they can extend this knowledge to novel problems (see Brown and Ferrara, 1985).

Brown's interest in measurement is characteristic of interventionist DA but is a clear parting of the ways from Vygotsky. She and her colleagues explicitly reference Vygotsky and the ZPD in explaining the theory of development underlying their approach (Campione et al., 1984). Indeed they praise Vygotsky's explication of the processes of development and the “interactive learning situations that provide structured guidance for the learner” (p. 80). However, while Vygotsky focused on optimally promoting development through mediation, Brown and colleagues are more interested in the “metric of learning efficiency”(p. 82), which they define as “the number of hints required for the attainment of the learning criterion”. Thus, although they include transfer of learning as part of their procedure, they are concerned with quantifying as an “index of speed of learning” (Brown and Ferrara, 1985, p. 300) the amount of help required for a learner to quickly and efficiently reach a pre-specified end point. Using a train metaphor, Elkonin (1998) states that those interested in speed and efficiency of learning are concerned with how quickly a train moves toward the final station along a set of tracks. Vygotsky, on the other hand, was not interested so much in the *speed* of the train along the already constructed track but with helping the person lay down *new* track leading toward a station that is potentially always being relocated (see Newman & Holzman, 1993).

While transfer tasks may bear a superficial similarity to using posttests in experimental research to ascertain the effects of a treatment, transfer in the Graduated Prompt Approach to DA can be distinguished by the continuing provision of mediation. That is, at no point in the procedure does the “treatment” end so that examinees are required to perform independently. Of course, if they do not encounter

problems, they do not receive mediation. However, the examiner is always ready to support them when their performance begins to breakdown. Linking sessions together in this way is a considerable advance in DA methodologies because, if followed to its logical conclusion, assessment and instruction are fully integrated (Poehner, 2008).

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